

Complexometric Titration of Tetravalent Vanadium

P. K. Bhattacharya

The formation and composition of a complex between ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid and vanadyl sulphate has been determined by Job's method, using $M/30$, $M/40$, and $M/60$ equimolar solutions. The greater stability of the VO.EDTA complex with respect to vanadyl catecholates has been determined by the colour change produced in the latter by titrating it against tetra-sodio salt of EDTA. The pH at which the colour of vanadyl catecholates is most intense has been determined. This complexometric titration has been suggested as a method of estimation of V(IV) in absence of the interfering radicals.

The bivalent vanadyl ion (VO^{2+}) is known to form complexes with oxalic acid¹ and other ligands². Catechol has been reported to form a complex with VO^{2+} which has an intense violet colour³. The formation of ethylenediamine hydrochloride⁴ and ethylenediamine tetra-acetate⁵ complexes of vanadyl ion has also been studied. This work has been undertaken in order to investigate the ethylenediamine tetra-acetate complex of VO^{2+} by Job's method⁶ and to utilise the high stability of the complex for the complexometric titration of V(IV), using catechol as an indicator.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of vanadyl sulphate (B.D.H.), ethylenediamine tetra-acetate (AnalaR), and catechol (B.D.H.) in conductivity water were used. The vanadium(IV) content of vanadyl sulphate was estimated by using ammonium benzoate as a precipitant⁷.

The composition of the complex formed was determined by Job's method⁶ of continuous variation, using $M/30$, $M/40$, and $M/60$ equimolar solutions of vanadyl sulphate and tetra-sodium salt of ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA). Measurements of conductance were carried out as usual. The curves (Fig. 1, A & B) exhibit maxima at 50% of the ligand, indicating the formation of a 1:1 complex.

Effect of pH.—The effect of H^+ -ion concentration on the absorbance of vanadyl catecholates complex was determined, using a Beckman colorimeter. The results are represented in Fig. 2. The absorbance goes on increasing to pH 3, but higher pH has hardly

1. Zolotarev and Kalugina, *Zhur. neorg. Khim.*, 1950, 1, 703.

2. Bhattacharya and Banerji, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, 21, 147; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 131.

3. *Idem*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1962, 315, 118.

4. Bhattacharya *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 240.

5. Schwarzenbach, "Complexometric Titrations", Translated by Irving, Methuen Co Ltd., London, p.8.

6. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

7. Shemyakin and Chapuignin, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1935, 8, 536.

any effect on the colour intensity. For titration, the pH of the solution to start with was therefore maintained at 3.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Complexometric Titration.—To vanadyl sulphate solution (10 ml) in a titration flask was added about an equimolar catechol solution (1 ml) and the solution kept aside for some time. It developed an intense violet colour due to formation of vanadyl catecholate. Now to this solution was added an equimolar EDTA solution from the burette. The violet colour of the solution at first faded away and a light blue colour finally appeared. The conversion from violet to blue colour took place at the point, where 10 ml of EDTA was added to 10 ml of equimolar vanadyl sulphate mixed with catechol, which was considered to be its end point.

This clearly indicates that EDTA forms a more stable complex than vanadyl catecholate. When EDTA is added to a mixture of vanadyl sulphate and catechol, it first reacts with the free VO^{2+} ions to form the complex. When all the free ions have been consumed, the further amount of EDTA added replaces catechol from vanadyl catecholate and takes up its place. At the end point, whole of the vanadyl catecholate is decomposed and hence the colour due to it disappears completely.

This substitution titration can be utilised for the estimation of VO^{2+} . Catechol is not known to show any colour reaction with many ions; presence of molybdenum and lead, however, interferes with the titration. In their absence, the estimation of tetravalent vanadium yielded satisfactory results.

TABLE I

V(IV) present in 10 ml (g.)	..	0.5095	0.1274	0.0319	0.0159
V(IV) found (g.)	..	0.5074	0.1269	0.0308	0.0152

The authors' thanks are due to Prof. S. M. Mukherji, Head of the Chemistry Department, for providing laboratory facilities.